

Original Research

Evaluation Of Change in Color and Translucency of Different Types of Provisional Restorative Materials Using Different Types of Temporary Dental Cements

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Provisional restorations play a critical role in prosthodontic therapy by maintaining function, aesthetics, and protection of prepared teeth. The final color of these restorations is influenced by material type, thickness, and underlying luting cement. **Methods:** This in vitro study evaluated the effect of two provisional restorative materials—self-cure polymethyl methacrylate (DPI) and bis-acryl composite (Luxatemp Fluorescence)—at two thicknesses (1 mm and 2 mm), using three temporary luting cements (Templute, TempoSIL, and Provicol). A total of 120 specimens were fabricated and divided into subgroups (n=10). Color and translucency were measured before and after cementation using a spectrophotometer. Data were analysed using two-way ANOVA, t-tests, and Tukey's post-hoc test ($p < 0.05$). **Results:** Significant differences in color change (ΔE) were observed based on material type, cement, and thickness ($p < 0.001$). DPI showed higher color change compared to Luxatemp at both thicknesses. Templute exhibited the highest color change, while Provicol showed the least. Thinner specimens (1 mm) demonstrated greater color variation and translucency changes.

Conclusion: Material composition, restoration thickness, and type of temporary cement significantly influence the optical properties of provisional restorations. Bis-acryl materials with silicone-based cements are recommended for superior aesthetic outcomes.

Keywords: Provisional restorative materials, Color stability, Translucency, Temporary cements, Spectrophotometer.

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INTRODUCTION

Provisional restorations are an essential component of fixed prosthodontic therapy. The term “provisional” refers to a temporary restoration provided until placement of a definitive prosthesis.¹ These restorations protect prepared teeth, maintain occlusal function, and preserve aesthetics during treatment.² They act as thermal insulators that protects the prepared tooth structure, stabilize occlusal relationships, and allow evaluation of functional and aesthetic outcomes prior to definitive prosthesis placement.³ Ideally, provisional restorations should

closely mimic definitive restorations in all aspects except material composition.

Various materials such as polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), polyvinyl methacrylate, polyethylene methacrylate, bis-acryl composites, and urethane methacrylate are commonly used.⁴ These materials must exhibit adequate strength, biocompatibility, wear resistance, and aesthetic stability. In aesthetically critical areas, color stability and stain resistance are particularly important.⁵

Despite the widespread use of bis-acryl resins, acrylic resins are still preferred in certain clinical situations. The final color of provisional restorations is

influenced not only by the restorative material but also by the underlying tooth structure and luting cement, especially in thin restorations, so making careful selection of the cement is crucial in the esthetic zone.⁶

The purpose of this in vitro study was to evaluate the change in color and translucency of the two different provisional restorative materials at two different thicknesses, using three different commercially available temporary luting types of cement.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

In Vitro experimental study

Setting

Department of Prosthodontics and Crown & Bridge

Ethical Approval

Obtained from the institutional Ethical Review Board

Materials Used

Provisional materials:

Self-cure polymethyl methacrylate (DPI)

Bis-acryl composite (Luxatemp Fluorescence)

Temporary luting cements:

Templute

TempoSIL

Provicol

A stainless-steel mold was prepared according to ADA specification number 27. A total of 120 specimens were fabricated for the study according to study conducted by Correa et al.⁷The specimens were made from self-cure tooth moulding powder (DPI) and Luxatemp Fluorescence with 60 specimens prepared from each material.

For each provisional material, the specimens were further divided based on thickness into two groups: 30 specimens with diameter of 20mm and thickness of 2 mm and 30 specimens with 20mm of diameter and thickness of 1 mm. Thickness group was then subdivided into three subgroups (n = 10) according to the type of temporary luting cement used. Thus, specimens from DPI self-cure polymethyl methacrylate and Luxatemp bisacrylic composite were cemented using three different temporary cements—Templute, TempoSIL, and Provicol—resulting in six cementation subgroups per thickness. DPI Self-Cure and Luxatemp Fluorescence were mixed as per manufacturer's instructions, packed into molds of 20mm diameter and 1mm and 2mm thickness, pressed between glass slabs and polyester strips, and after the completion of the setting time set for 6 min, the specimen were then finished with 2400–4000 grit sandpaper Color coordinates were recorded using VITA Easyshade Advance 4.0 on white and black backgrounds (three readings averaged). Color and translucency change were measured before and after cementation with VITA Easyshade advance 4.0

Spectrophotometer to assess changes. All the data obtained were statistically evaluated.

Sample Size and Grouping

A total of 120 specimens were fabricated according to study conducted by Correa et al.⁷The specimens were made from self-cure tooth moulding powder (DPI) and Luxatemp Fluorescence with 60 specimens prepared from each material.

Divided into:

1 mm thickness (n=30)

2 mm thickness (n=30)

Thickness group was then subdivided into three subgroups (n = 10) according to the type of temporary luting cement used. Thus, specimens from DPI self-cure polymethyl methacrylate and Luxatemp bisacrylic composite were cemented using three different temporary cements—Templute, TempoSIL, and Provicol—resulting in six cementation subgroups per thickness (Figure-1). The armamentarium used were Dispensing gun, Stainless steel mold, glass slab, polyester slip. (Figure-2)

RESULT

Data obtained from 120 samples were statistically analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics software version 23. Descriptive statistics were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Inferential analysis was performed using two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), paired and unpaired t-tests, and post-hoc Tukey's multiple comparison test. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Color Change (ΔE) Evaluation

Two-way ANOVA analysis

Two-way ANOVA revealed a statistically significant effect of temporary luting cement on the color change of both DPI and Luxatemp provisional restorative materials at 2 mm and 1 mm thicknesses.

For DPI:

- At 2 mm thickness, a significant difference was observed ($F = 29.633, p < 0.001$).
- At 1 mm thickness, a highly significant difference was observed ($F = 368.345, p < 0.001$).

For Luxatemp:

- At 2 mm thickness, the difference was statistically significant ($F = 55.496, p < 0.001$).
- At 1 mm thickness, a highly significant difference was observed ($F = 249.516, p < 0.001$).

($F =$ ratio of variance between groups to variance within groups)

Inter-material comparison (Unpaired t-test)

A statistically significant difference in color change was observed between DPI and Luxatemp at both thicknesses with all three temporary luting cements.

At 2 mm thickness, DPI showed significantly higher color change than Luxatemp with all three temporary cements:

Templute ($p < 0.001$)

Temposil ($p < 0.001$)

Provicol ($p < 0.001$)

At 1 mm thickness, DPI exhibited significantly higher color change than Luxatemp with all three temporary luting cements ($p < 0.001$).

For DPI luted with Templute showed significantly higher color change compared to Temposil and Provicol ($p < 0.001$). DPI luted with Temposil also showed significantly higher color change than Provicol ($p = 0.032$).

For Luxatemp luted with Templute demonstrated significantly higher color change compared to Temposil and Provicol at both thicknesses ($p < 0.001$).

Mean color change values

At 2 mm thickness, the maximum color change was observed in DPI luted with Templute (5.62 ± 0.60), while the minimum color change was observed in Luxatemp luted with Temposil (1.30 ± 0.71).

At 1 mm thickness, DPI luted with Templute showed the highest color change (7.07 ± 0.29), whereas

Luxatemp luted with Provicol showed the lowest color change (2.65 ± 0.28). (Graph-1)

Overall, Luxatemp demonstrated significantly better color stability than DPI, and Provicol, while Templute resulted in the maximum color change in both materials. (Table-1) (Graph-2)

Post-hoc Tukey’s test

Post-hoc Tukey’s multiple comparison test demonstrated statistically significant intergroup differences among all three temporary luting cements for both materials at both thicknesses.

For DPI, Templute showed significantly higher color change compared to Temposil and Provicol ($p < 0.001$). DPI luted with Temposil also showed significantly higher color change than Provicol ($p = 0.032$).

For Luxatemp, Templute demonstrated significantly higher color change compared to Temposil and Provicol at both thicknesses ($p < 0.001$).

Figure: 1 Flow chart of sample fabrication

Fig 2: Armamentarium (Dispensing gun, Stainless steel mold, glass slab, polyester slip)

DPI Self-Cure and Luxatemp Fluorescence were mixed as per manufacturer’s instructions, packed into molds of 20mm diameter and 1mm and 2mm thickness, pressed between glass slabs and polyester strips, and after the completion of the setting time set for 6 min, the specimen were then finished with 2400–4000 grit sandpaper. (Figure-3), (Figure-4)

Color coordinates were recorded using VITA Easyshade Advance 4.0 on white and black backgrounds (three readings averaged) (Figure-5). Color and translucency change were measured before and after cementation with VITA Easyshade advance 4.0 Spectrophotometer to assess changes. All the data obtained were statistically evaluated. (Figure-6)

Figure 3: Fabrication of Luxatemp specimen

Figure 4: Fabrication of DPISelf-Cure specimen

Figure5: Recording the baseline readings of specimens in white and black background

Figure: 6 Screen displays the color coordinates for the measured specimen.

Provisional Material	Templute (mean±SD)	Temposil (mean±SD)	Provicol(mean±SD)
2mm Thickness			
DPI	5.62±0.59	4.15±0.95	3.34±0.30
Luxatemp	4.60±0.92	1.30±0.71	1.95±0.53
Unpaired t test	0.009	<0.001	<0.001
(P-value)	(significant)	(significant)	(significant)
1mm Thickness			
DPI	7.07±0.29	4.94±0.18	4.72±0.15
Luxatemp	6.15±0.38	4.02±0.39	2.65±0.28
Unpaired t test	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
(P-value)	(significant)	(significant)	(significant)

Table: 1 Mean, standard deviation and unpaired t-test of color change in DPI and Luxatemp material with three temporary luting cements at 2mm and 1mm of thickness.

Graph 1: Colour change of DPI provisional restorative material after cementation with various temporary luting cement

Graph:2 Colour change of Luxatemp provisional restorative material after cementation with various temporary luting cements

DISCUSSION

Esthetic acceptability of provisional restorations is a key determinant of clinical success, especially during prolonged prosthetic rehabilitation when patients are highly sensitive to color discrepancies. Color stability and translucency are therefore critical properties of provisional restorative materials, as emphasized by several authors.⁸ The present study evaluated the influence of provisional material type, temporary luting cement, and restoration thickness on color change and translucency after cementation.

The results demonstrated that color change (ΔE) and translucency were significantly affected by the type of provisional restorative material, cement, and thickness. Similar observations have been reported by Correia et al., who concluded that interim cement significantly influences color, translucency, and fluorescence of provisional restorations.⁷

In the present study, acrylic resin (DPI) showed significantly higher ΔE values compared to bis-acrylic resin (Luxatemp), irrespective of cement type and thickness. This finding is consistent with studies by Yannikakis et al.,⁹ and Scotti et al.,¹⁰ who reported

unpredictable and material-dependent color stability of provisional resins. The greater color change was observed in acrylic resin may be due to its PMMA-based homogeneous structure without filler particles, making it more susceptible to cement shade influence and water sorption. Doray et al.,¹¹ and Haselton et al.,¹² also reported that color stability is material-specific rather than category-dependent.

Bis-acrylic resin demonstrated superior color stability, due to the presence of inorganic filler particles within an organic resin matrix. Similar findings have been supported by studies highlighting the role of filler content, monomer chemistry, and polymerization efficiency in improving optical stability.¹³

Among the temporary luting cements evaluated, Provicol demonstrated the least color change with both provisional materials at both thicknesses, whereas Templute showed the highest ΔE values. These findings are in agreement with Correia et al.⁷ and Malkondu et al.,¹⁴ who reported that cement composition, opacity, and fluorescence significantly influence the final color of restorative materials, particularly in thinner restorations.

Restoration thickness significantly influenced both color change and translucency. Specimens with 1 mm thickness showed higher ΔE values and greater translucency changes compared to 2 mm thickness. This finding corroborates studies by Baldissara et al.,¹⁵ Kurtulmus et al.,¹⁶ and Wang et al.,¹⁷ who reported decreased translucency with increased material thickness. Thinner restorations allow greater light transmission, thereby increasing the influence of cement color on the final appearance.

Translucency values were lower for acrylic resin compared to bis-acrylic resin, which may be attributed to differences in internal light scattering mechanisms. Templute exhibited higher opacity, improving masking ability but potentially compromising aesthetics in high-visibility areas. DPI luted with Provicol showed minimal translucency change, suggesting its suitability for aesthetically demanding provisional restorations.¹⁸

Within the limitations of this study, it can be concluded that the optical properties of provisional restorations are influenced by a combination of material composition, luting cement type, and restoration thickness. Careful selection of provisional restorative material and temporary luting cement is therefore essential to achieve optimal esthetic outcomes during provisionalisation.

CONCLUSION

The optical properties of provisional restorative materials are influenced by both the material composition and the type of temporary cement used. Bis-acryl resin-based materials and silicone-based cements provide superior color and translucency stability and are recommended for anterior provisional restorations.

Within the limitations of this in vitro study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Color and translucency values of provisional restorative materials differed significantly at 1 mm and 2 mm thicknesses.
2. Reduction in thickness from 2 mm to 1 mm significantly increased translucency and enhanced the influence of cement on color alteration.
3. The type of temporary luting cement affected the color and translucency of both provisional materials.
4. All temporary cements evaluated demonstrated a reduction in translucency of the provisional restorations.
5. DPI (acrylic resin) exhibited greater changes in color and translucency compared to Luxatemp (bis-acrylic resin).
6. Among the cements tested, Provicol showed the least color alteration, whereas Templute demonstrated the maximum change in color and translucency.

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